

THE CONSOLIDATION OF GLASS FIBRE-POLYPROPYLENE TOWPREGS

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SUMMARY: In this work a theoretical model describing the consolidation of glass fibre-polypropylene (GF/PP) towpregs into composites by compression moulding is studied. Such model relates the constant pressure applied by the press to the other processing operational (consolidation time and temperature) and material variables (fibre/polymer content and packing arrangement, matrix viscosity and powder and fibre dimensions).

Compression tests were carried at different temperatures and constant press pressures on unidirectional GF/PP towpreg preforms. The experimentally determined displacement/time curves were compared to the model simulations assuming an isothermal consolidation and two different fibre/polymer packing arrangements, one triangular and the other hexagonal. The results obtained showed that the towpreg consolidation could be successfully predicted using the model under study.

KEYWORDS: Modelling, Isothermal consolidation, Compression moulding, Glass fibres, Thermoplastic matrix composites, Towpregs, Powder coating process, Polypropylene.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic matrices may be advantageously employed in substitution of thermosetting ones to produce long fibre reinforced structural composites [1]. The impregnation of long fibres with the thermoplastic brings difficulties that can, however, be successfully overcome through the use of powder-coated towpregs [2, 3].

The phenomena occurring during the consolidation of powder-coated towpregs largely affect the properties of composites processed from them. In this work a theoretical model describing the consolidation of glass fibre-polypropylene (GF/PP) towpregs into composites by compression moulding is studied. Such model relates the constant pressure applied by the press to the other processing operational (consolidation time and temperature) and material variables (fibre/polymer content and packing arrangement, matrix viscosity and powder and fibre dimensions).

A recently developed technology for coating continuous fibres with polymer powders at low cost [4-7] allowing the efficient production of thermoplastic towpregs was used in the work.

THEORY

The powder coated thermoplastic matrix towpregs (Fig. 1) can be considered as a lamina of fibres with polymer particles attached. To produce a composite a determined number of these lamina are stacked together and placed in a mould to be compressed at a certain temperature and pressure during the time necessary to obtain full consolidation (t_{imp}).

Fig. 1: Schematic towpreg representation.

The estimation of the consolidation time is made through a theoretical model proposed elsewhere [8] that assumes: i) material incompressibility; ii) the fibres are regularly organized in the lamina in triangular or hexagonal arrangement (Fig. 1b)); iii) at the beginning of the consolidation, each polymer particle forms a bridge with length $2l_0$ between adjacent fibres; iv) upon compression the bridges spread in the direction of the fibres; v) the applied pressure is constant; vi) the polymer flow is considered laminar and steady.

By considering the length of the polymer particle $2L$ at the end of consolidation, at any instant the time spent from the beginning of the process, t , can be related with the bridge instantaneous length, ℓ :

$$t = \frac{\eta \cdot C}{P_a} \left(\frac{r_p}{r_f} \right)^6 \left(\frac{v_{ff}}{v_{pf}} \right)^4 \left(\frac{\ell}{L} \right)^5 \quad (1)$$

where η is the polymer viscosity, P_a is the applied pressure, C is a constant depending on the fibre/polymer arrangement, r_p and r_f are the radii and v_{pf} and v_{ff} the final volume fractions of the polymer and fibre, respectively. For the triangular and hexagonal fibre/polymer packing arrangements considered the values of constant C were calculated from the geometrical considerations as $128/135$ and $8/135$, respectively.

At any instant of the compression process the ratio ℓ/L can be also correlated with the instantaneous, h , and final, h_f , total measured laminate thickness, by:

$$\frac{h}{h_f} = 1 - \frac{1 - \frac{\ell}{L}}{1 + \frac{\ell v_{ff}}{L v_{pf}}} \quad (2)$$

If the applied pressure and mould temperature are kept constant during compression, Eq. (1) can be rewritten as:

$$t = K \cdot \left(\frac{\ell}{L}\right)^5 \quad (3)$$

where K is a constant depending on the processing conditions, fibre/polymer arrangement and materials' properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Raw-materials

Glass fibres (2400 Tex 357D-AA, supplied by Owens Corning) and a polypropylene powder (ICORENE 9184B P, supplied by ICO Polymers France) were used to produce the towpregs used in this work. The polymer and fibres have densities of 0.905 and 2.56 Mg/m³, respectively. Figure 2 shows the typical shape of polypropylene particles observed under SEM microscopy.

Fig. 2: PP powder under SEM, a) 65×, b) 270×

The polypropylene particle size was determined by sieving. The results obtained were fitted with good correlation using a Weibull distribution. Table 1 summarizes the values obtained for the particle diameter in terms of mass and number of particles. The value determined for the mean polypropylene particle diameter in terms of number of particle was used as PP particle diameter in the calculations made in this work.

Table 1: Obtained PP sieving results.

Property	Units	Mass of particles	Number of particles
Mean particle diameter	μm	381	163
Median particle diameter	μm	362	136
Variance	μm^2	27155	8991

The viscosity of the polypropylene was measured at four different temperatures (200, 240, 280 and 320 °C) using a TA Instruments Weissenberg rheogoniometer working in oscillatory mode from 1 to 31.6 Hz. At each temperature, 3 discs made by compression moulding with a diameter of 25 mm and a thickness of 0.9 mm were tested.

An Arrhenius law was considered for the polypropylene viscosity dependence on temperature, which means:

$$\eta = 0.16e^{\frac{4409}{T}} \dot{\gamma}^{-0.21} \quad (4)$$

where the shear rate, $\dot{\gamma}$, was considered as the average value determined for initial and final consolidation instants by the equation:

$$\dot{\gamma} = \frac{\left(\frac{2(\ell - \ell_0)}{t} \right)}{\left(\frac{d + 2\ell_0}{2} \right)} \quad (5)$$

where d is the distance between two adjacent fibres (see Fig. 1b)).

Compression moulding

A mould with a 100X100 mm cavity, mounted in an instrumented 400 kN SATIM press, was used to consolidate the unidirectional laminate in composite plates at two different temperatures (240 and 260 °C) and pressures (10 and 15 MPa). For each condition three samples were consolidated. In each experiment, the pressure and temperature were kept constant and the mould displacement were measured and recorded using an LVDT and a PC based acquisition system (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Experimental set-up.

The towpreg used in this work was produced in the powder coating line [4-7] using the processing conditions described elsewhere [6]. First, 16 m of towpreg wound on a mandrel were placed on the mould cavity. Then, the mould temperature was increased until the experimental temperature desired. After reaching the testing temperature, a 10 min delay was used to achieve uniform temperature on the composite. The press was then closed and the data acquisition began as soon as the test pressure was reached. The glass fibre volume fractions of the consolidated composite plates were measured using burn-off tests according to ISO 1172 standard. An average value of 70.0 ± 3.4 % was found.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows the experimental obtained curves from tests made at pressure of 10 MPa and temperature of 260°C. As can be seen, the laminate suffers a much higher thickness decreasing at the beginning of the consolidation process.

Fig. 4: Experimental curves of laminate thickness versus time.

The dimensionless experimentally obtained curves are compared with the theoretical ones calculated from the model for the triangular and hexagonal fibre/polymer packing arrangements in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: Comparision between theoretically and experimentally obtained curves.

As can be seen, all the experimental data fall between the theoretical values predicted for both fibre/polymer packing arrangements. However, the predictions for the hexagonal arrangement are in better agreement with the experimental results.

The discrepancies found between experimental results and theoretical simulations seem to be consequence of the difficulties found in establishing the real fibre/polymer arrangement and polymer flow conditions during consolidation. In fact, in Eq. (3), the parameter K is related with the fibre/polymer arrangement and the exponent results from the one-dimensional longitudinal polymer flow along the fibres considered in the model.

To take into account the possibility of transversal polymer flow and better characterize the real fibre/polymer arrangement, the Equation (3) can be modified to better fit the experimental data by the following generalized expression:

$$t = K_1 \cdot \left(\frac{\ell}{L} \right)^\alpha \quad (6)$$

where K_1 and α are constants to be determined experimentally.

Table 2 summarizes the values determined for the constants K_1 and α that better fit the consolidation of the towpreg tested in this work. Using these experimental parameters was possible to predict with much accuracy the material behaviour during processing.

Table 2: Values determined from the experimental results for the parameters K_1 and α .

Experimental conditions	K_1 (s)	α
260 °C – 15 MPa	250	4.2
240 °C – 15 MPa	416	4.4
260 °C – 10 MPa	1112	5.9
240 °C – 10 MPa	2024	4.1

The values of the constants in Table 2 were determined by fitting a least square line to the experimental curves. From the results obtained for these constants it can be concluded, as expected, that the parameter K_1 is more affect by the processing conditions than the parameter α .

CONCLUSIONS

The theoretical model used in this study can be used to predict the towpreg behaviour during consolidation by compression moulding.

The discrepancies found between experimental results and theoretical simulations seem to be consequence of the difficulties found in establishing the real fibre/polymer arrangement and polymer flow conditions during consolidation.

A new equation is proposed by this work, which includes two constants to be determined experimentally, to allow predicting with much more accuracy the towpregs behaviour during consolidation by compression moulding.

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